

CURRICULUM: FUNCTION, RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATION AND TEACHING

Akmal

Universitas Sultan Muhammad Syafiuddin Sambas

Akmalkece508@gmail.com

Abstract

The curriculum plays an important role in education both in educational institutions and in the community. The curriculum plays a role in shaping students ready to go into society. That way the curriculum must contain a conservative role so that students are able to transmit the cultural values of society so that students are able to preserve the cultural values of society and are not influenced by foreign cultures, creative roles so that students become more creative, innovative and constructive when facing various problems or conditions to be resolved and critical and evaluative roles so that students are able to filter cultural values that are still relevant to the times or conditions of society. The curriculum is closely related in education. Curriculum that is closely related in education. Where the curriculum is also a tool for developing education both through school education institutions, madrasas and Integrated Islamic Schools which have different educational goals. Where schools emphasize more knowledgeable students, madrasas that emphasize students have a strong religious foundation and the Integrated Islamic School emphasizes both broad knowledge which is fortified with strong religious knowledge.

Keyword: Curriculum, Function, Relationship Between, Education, Teaching

INTRODUCTION

The curriculum as an educational design has a very strategic position in all aspects of educational activities. Given the important role of the curriculum in education and in the development of human life, then the preparation of the curriculum can not be done without understanding the basic concepts of the curriculum. With the implementation of government policy (Depdiknas), namely the development of an operational curriculum carried out by each unit of education with the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP) programme, then all levels in each unit of education must have a broad and in-depth understanding of the basic concepts of the curriculum, and operationally should be used as a reference in implementing the curriculum in each unit of education it manages. Basically, the curriculum is a system consisting of several components. The components of the curriculum of an educational institution can be identified by examining the curriculum of the educational institution. From the book we can know the meaning and dimensions of the curriculum as well as the function and role of a curriculum component against other curriculum components. The curriculum serves as a guide in the implementation of educational activities in schools for the parties involved,

baim directly or indirectly, such as teachers, principals, supervisors, parents, communities and the students themselves. In addition to being a guide, for students the curriculum has six functions, namely: adjustment function, integration function, differentiation function, preparation function, selection function, and diagnostic function. Given the importance of a thorough understanding of the basic concepts of this curriculum, the author is moved to compile it into a paper that specifically reveals about it. Hopefully, the presence of this paper can open the insights of all readers a little.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method in this discussion is to use the library study method (library research), which is a method of collecting data by understanding and studying the theory of various literatures related to this discussion. The data collection also uses a way by looking for sources from various sources, for example: journals, books, and others. Literature obtained from various references is then analysed critically and deeply in order to support the propositions and ideas (DarmalaKsana, 2020).

DISCUSSION RESULTS

Definition of Curriculum

Etymologically, the curriculum comes from the Greek, namely *curir* and *curre*, which is a term for a place to race and run from a race that has formed a kind of race route and must be traversed by competitors. In other words, the route must be obeyed and travelled by competitors in a race. (Jeflin and Afriansyah, 2020). In Law No. 20 of 2003 Chapter 1 Article 1 states that 'Curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the objectives, content, and learning materials as well as the methods used as guidelines for organising learning activities to achieve certain educational goals' (Rohmadi, 2022). This states that the curriculum is a set of plans and regulations regarding the content and learning materials as well as the methods used as guidelines in the implementation of the teaching and learning process.

According to S. Nasution, the curriculum is a plan that is prepared to launch the teaching and learning process under the guidance and responsibility of schools or educational institutions and teaching staff. Furthermore, Nasution explained that a number of curriculum theorists argue that the curriculum not only includes all planned activities, but also events that occur under the supervision of the school. So in addition to formal curriculum activities which are often called co-curricular activities, but also extra- curricular (co-curriculum or extra curriculum).(Bahri, 2017) extra curriculum).(Bahri, 2017) According to al-Syaibani, the curriculum is a bright path travelled by educational institutions and educators to develop the potential, skills and knowledge of students, in accordance with educational

goals.(Khalilurrahman, 2021).

So, it can be concluded that the curriculum in education is the overall programme or learning activities at an educational institution in order to realise the vision, mission of the educational institution.

Curriculum Functions

The curriculum as an educational tool can be grouped into several functions, namely: curriculum as a development of children's cognitive processes, children's self- actualisation, social reconstruction, and academics.(Sukirman dan Nugraha, 2011)

First, the Curriculum Functions as a Cognitive Process. As a cognitive process, the curriculum is seen as a tool to develop children's intellectual abilities, namely the development of thinking skills to face and solve problems that will be faced.

Second, the Curriculum Functions as a Self-Actualisation Process. As a process of self-actualisation of children, the curriculum is a tool to facilitate children to grow and develop according to their potential, interests and talents so that each child can get to know himself and grow and develop as himself.

Third, the Curriculum Functions as a Social Reconstruction Process. As a social reconstruction process, the curriculum is seen as a tool to equip children with the ability to become members of society who not only accept or adapt to the existing 'life', but also innovatively and creatively develop life in a more productive and quality direction.

Fourth, the Curriculum Functions as an Academic Programme. As an academic programme, the curriculum is seen as a tool and a place of learning, where from the learning activities programmed by the curriculum children can gain knowledge which is expected to equip the ability to be able to 'live' in the era they are going through.

In connection with the function of the curriculum for students as well, in other literature mentioned by Alexander Inglis in Hamalik, that the function of the curriculum for students there are 6 (Six), namely: (Sudin, 2014);

First, the Adjustment Function (the adjustive or adaptive functiom). The adjustment function means that the curriculum as an educational tool must be able to direct students to have a well adjusted nature, which is able to adapt to the environment, both the physical environment and the social environment. The environment itself is constantly changing and dynamic. Therefore, students must also have the ability to adjust to changes that occur in their environment.

Second, the function of integration (the integrating function). The integration function means that the curriculum as an educational tool must be able to produce whole individuals. Students are basically members and integral parts of society. Therefore, students must have the personality needed to be able to live and

integrate with their society.

Third, the Differentiation Function (the differentiating function). The differentiation function means that the curriculum as an educational tool must be able to provide services to individual student differences. Each student has differences, both from the physical and psychological aspects, which must be respected and served properly.

Fourth, the Preparatory Function (the propaedeutic function). The preparatory function implies that the curriculum as an educational tool should be able to prepare students to continue their studies at the next level of education. In addition, the curriculum is also expected to prepare students to be able to live in society if he for some reason, can not continue his education.

Fifth, the Selection Function (the selective function). This means that the curriculum as an educational tool must be able to provide opportunities for students to choose learning programmes that suit their abilities and interests. This function is closely related to the function of differentiation because recognition of the individual differences of students also means the opportunity for these students to choose what suits their interests and abilities. To realise these two functions, the curriculum needs to be structured more broadly and flexibly (flexible).

Sixth, the Diagnostic Function (the diagnostic function). The diagnostic function means that the curriculum as an educational tool must be able to help and direct students to be able to understand and accept their strengths (potential) and weaknesses. If students are able to understand the strengths and weaknesses that exist in themselves, it is expected that students can develop their own potential / strengths or improve their weaknesses.

Definition of education and teaching

The term education comes from the Greek 'paedagogie' whose root words are 'pais' which means child and 'again' which means guidance. So 'paedagogie' means guidance given to children. In English, education is translated as 'Education'. Education comes from the Greek 'educare' which means to bring out what is stored in the soul of the child, to be guided to grow and develop.

Definition of education according to experts

Ki Hajar Dewantara, as an Indonesian National Education Figure, laying a strong foundation for progressive National education for present and future generations formulated the definition of education as follows: 'Education generally means efforts to advance the growth of character (inner strength, character), mind (intellect and body of the child); in Taman Siswa, these parts should not be separated so that we can advance the perfection of life, life and life of the children we educate, in harmony with the world'. This figure is a pioneer and founding father of the Taman Siswa school. The basis is now known as 'Panca Darma', the basics are; basic independence, basic nationality, basic humanity, basic culture and basic

natural nature. In its implementation, the basis of independence is intended so that educators provide freedom to students to regulate themselves and develop their own individuals, but must be based on high life values, so that balance and harmony can be realised both as individuals and as members of society. With the conception as described above, Dewantara has laid the foundation of the child's nature as the first and main factor which is famous for the slogan 'Let us serve the child' This ideal will be implemented if the child is given freedom and independence to become a civilised human being in accordance with the culture and respect for his own nation as an Indonesian nation.

John Dewey, an American philosopher of pragmatism and dynamic education, defined education as 'The process of forming fundamental intellectual and emotional skills towards nature and fellow human beings'. According to him, life is an ever-changing process, none of which is eternal. Because life is growth, education means helping inner growth without being limited by age. In other words, education is a human endeavour to assist growth in the process of life by forming fundamental skills or basic skills that include intellectual and emotional aspects that are useful or beneficial to humans, especially for themselves and for nature.

The various definitions above can be concluded that the essence of education is a process of human interaction between education and students to achieve educational goals. The process takes place in a certain environment by using various actions called educational tools.

Teaching is conveying knowledge to students as said by Kunandar (2007) that in the traditional view, teaching is interpreted as the transfer of culture in the form of knowledge, experience, and skills to students. This is really an old paradigm of teaching. This definition seems to see students as individuals who cannot do anything. Teachers feel all-knowing and have more abilities and knowledge than students. In the current context, it is undeniable that there are students who have more knowledge about something than the teacher because learning resources are everywhere. The presence of the internet today provides opportunities for anyone who wants to know more about anything. So, teachers have to change their old paradigm of teaching.

The relationship of education and teaching to the curriculum

Education is the process of transferring knowledge to individuals, while teaching is the implementation of the curriculum in the classroom, teachers design lesson plans and choose teaching methods in accordance with the objectives of the curriculum. Thus, the relationship between education, teaching, and curriculum creates an interrelated ecosystem of education. Education provides direction and goals, teaching implements lesson plans, while curriculum provides the structure and framework for both aspects. This whole system aims to achieve optimal educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Curriculum in education has orientation and function. First, cultural orientation, the results of the learning process in schools are expected to inherit the cultural foundations of society to the next generation. Second, personal orientation, so that the results of the learning process in schools are expected to equip students with the basic needs of individuals and groups. Third, vocational orientation, the results of the learning process are expected to equip students to actively participate in the real world. Fourth, social orientation, the results of the learning process at school are expected to enable students to be functional in society in realising common welfare. Fifth, economic orientation, the results of the learning process at school are expected to enable students to have individual abilities in contributing to the progress of the nation/country as a whole.

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